

POTENTIAL RISK FACTORS IN PATIENTS WITH AMI/ACS

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Objective: To assess the potential of major risk factors (RF) in patients with AMI/ACS (acute myocardial infarction/acute coronary syndrome) using the population of one of the districts of Samarkand aged 20-69 years as an example.

Material and methods: The present study was based on the data of the cohort study "Register of acute myocardial infarction and acute coronary syndrome in one of the districts of Samarkand . ACS and AMI were studied among the permanent population of one of the districts of Samarkand, the age of patients included in the study was 20-69 years (since the beginning of July 2009). The average age of the entire group was 58.5 ± 8.8 years, men - 56.8 ± 9.6 years, women - 61.6 ± 5.8 years. A total of 216 patients with AMI/ACS admitted to hospital over 9 months were identified. Among them, AMI was detected in 75 (34.7%) cases, ACS in 141 (65.3%) cases. The results showed that the frequency of AMI/ACS in men was 2 times higher than in women. In women, no cases of AMI/ACS were observed in the initial six five-year periods, while 30 (21.7%) cases of the pathology under study were detected in men during this period. Risk factor (RF) analysis showed that 28.2% of patients were smokers, with smokers occurring among men 5.5 times more often. Overweight (BMI) and/or obesity were observed in 76.8% of patients, with equal frequency among men and women. In the age group of 45-49 years, the incidence of this RF (obesity grades 1-3) was highest in men (82%) and women (93%) . Hypercholesterolemia (> 200 mg/ dL) was detected in 75 (34.7%) patients, including 44 (31.9%) men and 31 (39.7%) women. Analysis of the prevalence of hypercholesterolemia depending on age showed that the highest values of this indicator were observed among 60-64 year old men 11 (25.2%) and 65-69 year old women 12 (38.7%). Diabetes mellitus (DM) was suffered by 60 (27.8%) patients, women 2 times more often - (39.7% and 21.0%, respectively). Arterial hypertension (AH) was suffered by 77.3% of patients (72.5% of men and 85.9% of women), analysis by AH degrees showed that 28 (12.9%) had AH degree II, 10 (4.6%) - stage III. Anamnesis data showed that a burdened family history of coronary heart disease was observed in 113 (52.3%) men and women. This indicator did not differ significantly between men and women (50.7% and 55.1%, respectively). In the group as a whole, 87 patients (40.2%) had suffered AMI in the past, including 58 (42.0%) men and 29 (37.2%) women, stable angina pectoris was suffered equally by men and women (66.6% and 73.0%, respectively).

Conclusions: The study demonstrated the highest prevalence of AMI/ACS in the age group of 65-69 years. At the same time, the potential of the underlying risk factors among men and women with AMI/ACS had its own characteristics: BMI was most common in the age groups of 45-49 years and 55-59 years, respectively, in men and women. Hypercholesterolemia and

hypertension were more often observed among women, while smoking was more typical for men.

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